

Biological Active Agents. Synthesis of Bakuchiol Analogues

BALDEV VIG and RAM KANWAR

Department of Chemistry, Maharshi Dayanand University, Rohtak-124 001

and

DESH RAJ ARORA

Department of Microbiology, Medical College, Rohtak

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Several bakuchiol analogues have been synthesised by preparing allyl vinyl ether of geraniol which on thermal rearrangement gave γ - δ -unsaturated aldehyde, which on further Grignard reaction with various substituted bromo aromatic compounds and dehydration gave various substituted analogues of title compounds. Their biological activities have been studied.

BAKUCHIOL has been isolated as an active oil from the seeds of *Psoralea corlifolia* Linn¹. (Sanskrit: *Bakuchi Sungandha Kantak*, Hindi: *Babchi*). During pharmacological screening^{2,3} it was noted that the oil inhibited the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus* in a concentration of 2-4 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. On the basis of chemical reactions, spectral data and synthesis⁴⁻⁷, bakuchiol has been shown to be monoterpene-phenol of having the structure, 1-(*p*-anisyl)-3,7-dimethyl-3-vinyl-1,6-octadiene (I, R=OH), b.p. 180-190°/11-15 mm. Because of its antibacterial activity it was thought of interest to prepare bakuchiol analogues and test their biological activity.

I', R = OH
I, R = H
II, R = CH₃
IV, R = OCH₃
V, R = OC₂H₅
VI, R = NO₂

III

Geraniol was converted to its vinyl ether through equilibration with ethyl vinyl ether in presence of mercuric acetate. Pyrolysis of the allyl-vinyl system in a sealed tube under nitrogen atmosphere generated 3,7-dimethyl-3-vinyl-oct-6-enal. The resulting γ - δ -unsaturated aldehyde was subjected to Grignard reaction with different *para*-substituted phenyl magnesium bromide to produce the corresponding carbinol which was subsequently dehydrated under milder conditions using POCl₃ in pyridine at low temperature. The final products were chromatographed

over alumina before distillation under reduced pressure. The purity of the compounds were checked on tlc and the structure of final analogues and various intermediates were checked through ir and ¹H nmr spectroscopy. Various analogues of bakuchiol prepared are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Sl. no.	Compd.	R	Mol. formula	B.p. °C/8 mm
1.	I	H	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	170-175°
2.	II	CH ₃	C ₁₆ H ₂₆	175-180°
3.	IV	OCH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ O	175-180°
4.	V	OC ₂ H ₅	C ₁₉ H ₂₈ O	185-190°
5.	VI	NO ₂	C ₁₅ H ₂₃ NO ₂	180-185°
6.	III		C ₂₃ H ₃₆	190-195°

The compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

Antibacterial activity :

Antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhi*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and antifungal activity against *Candida albicans*, *Cryptococcus neoformans*, *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*, *Microsporum canis* and *Aspergillus flavus* of all the compounds (I-VI) were studied as follows.

10 mg of each compound was dissolved in 10 ml each of absolute alcohol. Filter paper discs (6 mm dia.) cut from Whatman No. 1 were dipped in each of the above solution and the solvent was allowed to evaporate. Nutrient agar plates were inoculated with various bacteria, *C. albicans* and *C. neoformans*. On each plate one disc from each compound was applied and the plates inoculated with bacterial cultures were incubated at 37° for 18 h and those inoculated with fungi (*C. albicans* and *C. neoformans*) at 37° for 96 h. Zones of inhibition around the discs were noted. These showing these zones were taken as sensitive. Minimum inhibitory

TABLE 2—MINIMUM INHIBITORY CONCENTRATION OF COMPOUNDS (I-VI) IN $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ AGAINST VARIOUS BACTERIA AND FUNGI

Sl. no.	Organism	Minimum inhibitory concentration in $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$					
		Compound number					
		I	II	III	IV	V	VI
1.	<i>S. aureus</i>	—	—	neat	—	—	—
2.	<i>B. subtilis</i>	100	100	125	—	300	50
3.	<i>E. coli</i>	—	—	neat	—	100	—
4.	<i>S. typhi</i>	—	—	neat	—	—	—
5.	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	—	—	neat	—	—	—
6.	<i>C. albicans</i>	neat	neat	—	neat	—	—
7.	<i>C. neoformans</i>	neat	neat	125	neat	—	200
8.	<i>T. mentagrophytes</i>	>1000	100	125	>1000	>1000	>1000
9.	<i>M. canis</i>	150	125	>1000	50	50	100
10.	<i>A. flavus</i>	>1000	>1000	>1000	25	25	>1000

concentration (M.I.C.) of the compounds against the bacteria and fungi which were found to be sensitive to them in neat concentration were studied by serial plate dilution method. Minimum concentration of the compound showing no growth was taken as M.I.C. The M.I.C. of these compounds against *T. mentagrophytes*, *M. canis* and *A. flavus* were studied directly by serial dilutions of these compounds in Sabourand's dextrose agar and studied as above. Results of the present study indicate that the compounds are active against various bacteria and fungi. Compound III was the most active and showed antibacterial (gram-positive and gram-negative) and antifungal activity.

Juvenile hormone activity: All the compounds were tested for their JH activity on common Indian red cotton bug. The treatment was given within 24 h of moulting to the fifth instars. Perfect adults were scored as zero. An abnormal adult that

retained any of the fifth instar character scored one, one that died during moulting scored two and which could not moult scored three. The score of four was obtained by sixth instar. Average rating was calculated by multiplying the number of fifth instars by their numerical activity rating and divided the sum by the number of insects tested. The dead insects were excluded. The activities of the various compounds are given in the Table 3.

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TABLE 3—JUVENILE HORMONE ACTIVITY OF ANALOGUES OF BAKUCHIOL (I-VI) NUMBER OF INSECT = 10, DOSE % IN ACETONE (μ) = 6

Bakuchiol analogue	Dead	Activity response					Activity index
		0	1	2	3	4	
I	0	2	1	1	2	4	2.5
II	0	1	1	1	4	3	2.7
III	1	2	0	1	2	4	2.6
IV	0	1	1	1	1	6	3.0
V	0	1	0	2	2	5	3.0
VI	0	1	0	2	1	6	3.1